

Resurgence of Military Regimes in Three West African States: Threat to Democratic Rule

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Abstract

The recent resurgence of military regimes in Mali, Burkina Faso, and Guinea is a harrowing development in the democratic trajectory of West Africa. This study investigates the failure of democratic governments to secure territorial enclaves, provide minimum infrastructural amenities and services which has eroded trust of the citizens in the democratic order. The objective explored inclusive governance reform strategies viable to address citizen grievances and restore confidence in democratic institutions. Critical Democratic Theory derived from critical theory (Habermas, 1984) and radical democracy (Mouffe, 2000) is engaged as the lens through which the problematic is viewed. The methodology adopts a qualitative comparative approach, employing content analysis of policy briefs, scholarly literature, and communiqués of ECOWAS and the African Union. The findings reveal that the democratic institutions were bedeviled by weak rule of law, politicized judiciaries, and electoral manipulation leading to loss of public confidence in democratic processes among others. The study concludes that while the coups confirm deep structural weaknesses, they also indicate the weakness of externally imposed democratic frameworks that fail to address the domestic contexts of the three states. Lastly, the strengthening of regional mechanisms for democratic accountability and the implementation of inclusive governance reforms that ameliorate citizen grievances are recommended to safeguard democracy in the region. While the military should be saddled with the security of the state, lives and properties of citizens and not governance.

Keywords: military coups, democracy, West Africa, governance, political instability.

1.0. Introduction

The institutionalization of democratic norms in Africa, especially since the early 1990s, has been seen as the zenith of progress in the postcolonial politics of the African continent. However, the persistent reports of coup d'états in Mali (2020 and 2021), Guinea (2021), and Burkina Faso (2022 and 2023) have put to trial the existing positive narratives of democracy consolidation in the West African sub region lately. These occurrences not only represent a major alteration in leadership but also raise deep questions about the resilience of democratic institutions, the role of regional and international players, and the legitimacy of political authority in volatile settings.

In contrast with earlier coup d'etats stimulated by Cold War alignments and ideological competitions, contemporary coups are legitimized by national insecurity, misappropriation of public funds, and failure of governance narratives. Military rule in these states has therefore presented itself as the only respite option, whose skill of rule offer tenets that are close to good governance. Thus, attracting significant national empathy amid prevalent popular disappointment with the political elites. This study attempts to investigate the resurgence of military regimes in a more nuanced analytical framework that situates West Africa's democratic reversals within systemic and historical continuities, through the aid of appropriate theoretical insights from comparative democratization and postcolonial state concepts.

The feebleness of state institutions across many West African states has its roots deep in history. The legacies of colonialism under centralized authoritarianism, combined with post-independent personalized power structure, established governance patterns with the mindset to capture the elite class interests at the expense of large-scale development. This historical path of dependency has rendered democratic governance vulnerable to collapses at the first sign of crisis, particularly in environments where state legitimacy remains challenged and fractured.

Besides, democratic organizations and apparatus in the region has been externally driven, with global players and donor agencies emphasizing elections and democratization process as conditionalities for strategic collaborations and alliances as well as requirements to access grants and loans from these developed economies. This indeed opposed to substantial democratic values where structures for engagement have been thoroughly digested by the concerned state and can be adopted within the framework of practicability in their political clime. The result therefore, is visible disconnect between governance culture and citizens' demands of good governance traits, creating tension, agitations and conflictual tendencies. The recent military interventions resonate with a part of citizens who view liberal democracy as an elite agenda whose effects do not reflect in the practical socio – economic challenges of the populace.

The resurgence of coups also has re-emerged as a response to growing insecurity and socio-economic breakdown. Throughout the Sahelian states, extremist turbulence and rural disillusionment are rampant, the failure of civilian governments to secure territorial enclaves or provide minimum services and infrastructural amenities has eroded trust in the civilian democratic order. The military which serves as an institution that imposes order, through the use of force has won the sympathy and trust of these vulnerable citizens. The question that readily comes to mind here is what the future of democratic government in the region holds. To this end, this study investigates Resurgence of Military Regimes in Three West African States: Threat to Democratic Rule

The Research Objectives:

1. To examine the basis of public disillusionment with democratic governments in Mali, Burkina Faso, and Guinea that have contributed to support for military interventions.
2. To explore inclusive governance reform strategies viable to address citizen grievances and restore confidence in democratic institutions.
3. To understudy existing regional mechanisms (ECOWAS) in preventing military takeovers, safeguard democratic rule in West Africa and recommend more effective strategies.

Research Questions:

1. What factors fuel public disillusionment with democratic governments in Mali, Burkina Faso, and Guinea and contributed to the resurgence of military interventions?
2. What inclusive governance reform strategies can effectively address citizen grievances and restore public confidence in democratic institutions in West Africa?
3. How effective are existing ECOWAS mechanisms in preventing military takeovers and safeguarding democratic rule in West Africa, and what strategies can enhance their impact?

2.0. Literature Review

Re-emergence of West African military regimes has generated new scholarly and policy interest in the fragility of democratic transitions and the resilience of democratic rule in the region. Historically, the post-colonial politics of West Africa were marked by successive experiences with military coups, generally justified under the rhetoric of correcting corruption, incompetence, and political instability (Decalo, 1990). However, the 1990s witnessed a period of robust democratic movement that saw a general erosion of military interventions and the hardening of civilian control mechanisms, partly spurred by both international pressures and domestic civil society engagements (Gyimah-Boadi, 2001).

Quite recently political developments in Mali, Guinea, and Burkina Faso, however, point towards a disturbing reverse trend. These states have experienced military revolutions between 2020 and 2022, which speaks to the feebleness of the kind of democratic institutions built in these states. Symbolizing that, democratic governance tenets were only presumed to have gained foundation as the outcomes are contrary. According to Aning and Bah (2022), the military comeback does not just represent a democratic reversal but also indicates deepening disillusionment by the populace; especially the youth who have witnessed the incompetence, corrupt, and exclusionary democratic regimes. These circumstances offer prospects for armed players to restore their positions as alternative political arbiters, typically couched in the populist ideology of reform and national redemptive plights.

The literature identifies interconnected drivers for such regression, first, is the decline of constitutional norms, through incumbents manipulating terms of engagements and seeking to elongate their tenure limits constitutionally. Writers like Cheeseman and Klaas (2018) argue that such a practice weakens the legitimacy of democratic processes and welcomes the emergence of military opportunism. The 2021 coup in Guinea, for example, followed President Alpha Condé's controversial bid for a third term, which was found to be unconstitutional and undemocratic by the consensus.

Secondly, weak state capacity and poor governance have been long-standing issues. A study by Olonisakin and Okech (2020) points out that when governments fail to provide security, justice, and economic possibility, public trust dissipates, and the military is left to fill the resulting vacuum. The Mali example is insightful: pervasive insecurity from jihadist insurgencies in the north, combined with public perceptions of government ineptitude, set the stage for the 2020 coup and its 2021 sequel (Wing, 2021).

Third, there have been inconsistent, weak, or even mixed external responses to such coups, which scholars portend would often provide incentives to military adventurism. While regional actors like

ECOWAS have generally had robust anti-coup norms - such as in the 2001 Protocol on Democracy and Good Governance - recent responses have been criticized for not having enforcement teeth. In the views of Adebani (2022), he states that, failure to impose meaningful and sustained sanctions has undermined the legitimacy of regional assertions of democratic norms.

Theoretically, the re-emergence of military regimes discredits the model of transition which had assumed linear development from authoritarianism to consolidated democracy (Carothers, 2002). It reinforces the contention of analysts like Bratton and van de Walle (1997) that African democratization is highly contingent on elite bargains, institutional strength, and socio-political inclusiveness. Without them, transitions become reversible. These events in West Africa also fall into Bratton's (2013) theory of 'democratic recession', where development within the third wave of democratization is unwound and slowed down through authoritarian reassertion, institutional breakdown, or manipulation of elections.

Moreover, further literature examined the popular view of the military in governance. Perceive it as coercive state tools in history, as such the current explanation presents a complex situation, where armies are occasionally viewed as neutral actors in the middle of partisan civilian crises (Albrecht & Jackson, 2020). This view can legitimize coups by the people, particularly if the civic space has been shut and electoral processes undermined.

Therefore, these renewed instances of military rule in Mali, Guinea, and Burkina Faso point to a structural and ideological crisis in West African democracies. Scholars consistently point to the failure of democratic governments to provide good governance, feeble constitutionalism, and a poor response to the grievances of the citizens as being primary. It also condemns the weak reactions of the international community, and challenges the notion that democracy is guaranteed in post-coup scenarios. Further scholarly research on these subject calls for fresh attention to democratic resilience, civil-military relations, and socio-political conditions that incline states toward democratic consolidation and not military capture.

3.0. Theoretical Underpinnings

The restoration of military rule contradicts the transition model that had assumed a linear change from authoritarianism to democracy (Carothers, 2002). It also validates Bratton and van de Walle's (1997) view that African democratization is built on elite consensus, institutional strength, and socio-political inclusiveness. Without these, democracy is prone to authoritarian relapsing.

Be that as it may, Critical Democratic Theory provide the lenses through which this discourse could be viewed. It interrogates the power structures and exclusions within liberal democracies, supporting participatory, inclusive, and emancipatory governmental policies and implementation. Derived from critical theory (Habermas, 1984) and radical democracy (Mouffe, 2000) it exposes systemic inequalities and strengthen democratic tenets through reflexiveness, contestation, and pluralism (Young, 2000; Fraser, 2009). Its' interest in measuring the performance and assessing the legitimacy of democratic institutions beyond procedure avers that poor representation index of governments routinely induces poor performance connected to corruption, agitations and unrest. Postcolonial state theory is employed to guide the understanding of structural vulnerabilities and contested sovereignties characteristic of post-independence African states. These theoretical frameworks provide clues to the perceptions that often sustain unstable character of state power under democratic regimes in Africa. It equally offers insight into how the legitimacy and sovereignty of states are hybridized by structural vulnerabilities.

Also, the popular perceptions of the military as neutral or possessing redressive abilities, particularly in corrupt or crisis-ridden civilian governments. As such, it makes the normative rebuff of military rule increasingly complicated (Albrecht & Jackson, 2020). This sort of 'legitimacy' through public perception further erodes democratic norms, while enabling military actors to exploit the 'awarded trust'

of popular opinion in the event of widespread grouse and grievances against the lapses of the kind of democratic rule being practiced in West Africa.

4.0. Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative comparative approach, employing content analysis of policy briefs, scholarly literature, and communiqués of regional bodies such as ECOWAS and the African Union. Analytically, critical democratic theory guides the critique, which is interested in measuring the performance and assessing the legitimacy of democratic institutions beyond proceduralism. Postcolonial state theory also guides understanding of structural vulnerabilities and contested sovereignties characteristic of post-independence African states. These theoretical frameworks provide clues to the perceptions that often sustain unstable character of state power under democratic regimes in Africa. It equally offers insight into how the legitimacy and sovereignty of states are hybridized by structural vulnerabilities.

Case selection was deliberate: Mali, Guinea, and Burkina Faso were chosen because they constitute the three states where successful coups recently took effect. Moreso, the local and international wide-ranging responses advertised the popularity of this subject so well, that it deserves a methodical review and contribution. Political events in each of the three states from 2018 through 2024 were compared by the researchers in similarities and differences on their paths to military rule.

5.0. Results

The research enunciates four broad themes underlying the resurgence of military rule in the selected states:

Institutional Erosion and Elite Failure: In all three cases, democratic institutions suffered from weak rule of law, politicized judiciaries, and electoral manipulation. Civilian regimes lost legitimacy as they became more corrupt, mismanaged the economy, and practiced nepotism. Theoretically, this is in line with elite theory, which holds that democratic regimes in fragile states are likely to be elite preservation mechanisms rather than mass inclusion.

Popular Disenchantment: A dramatic loss of public confidence in democratic processes was observed, with citizens viewing elections as elite power struggles rather than accountability mechanisms. In each case, the military had initial popular support, casting itself as a corrective force rather than a usurper. This is in consonance with legitimation theory, which posits perceptions of efficacy and justice to be determinative of the longevity of political regimes.

Security Crises: Widespread insecurity, in particular from communal violence and jihadist insurgencies, created legitimacy deficits that military actors exploited. In Burkina Faso and Mali in particular, civilian regimes appeared powerless to halt violence, allowing the military to pose intervention as a matter of national necessity. Theorists of the security–development nexus point to the role of insecurity as a catalyst for regime change, especially in weak state environments.

Regional and International Ambiguity: Although ECOWAS and the African Union condemned the coups and imposed sanctions, their enforcement was irregular, and some international actors exhibited ambivalence, especially where there were geopolitical interests at stake. This scenario demonstrates dependency theory, which emphasizes the structural constraints imposed on African sovereignty and governance autonomy by external actors.

6.0. Discussion and Finding

The re-emergence of military governments in West Africa portends more than episodic democratic reversals - it signals the underlying contradictions of the continent's democratic experiment. The imposition of liberal democratic institutions in the absence of a solid socio-political foundation has resulted in superficial democratization, vulnerable to collapse under pressure.

These shifts require a reframing of democratic promotion in Africa. Foreign donors and regional actors must go beyond Eurocentric standards and encourage governance structures with foundations in local legitimacy, social compacts, and inclusive politics. Theoretically, this requires embracing decolonial insights on governance, which undermine Eurocentricity and move in search of indigenous and context-sensitive forms of political legitimacy.

At the same time, West African societies must contend with the difficult task of rebuilding confidence in democratic governance, institution-building, and resisting authoritarian backsliding -both military and civilian. A more grounded democratic theory must pose not only questions regarding the procedural prerequisites of governance but also regarding the underlying cultural, historical, and ideological forces propelling political power in Africa.

Finally, as desirable as military coups in Mali, Guinea, and Burkina Faso may appear as short-term solutions to government failure, they actually pose real threats to democratic leadership, as well as regional stability. Indeed, attacking these symptoms instead of the disease of democratic weakness is still the most viable path to follow.

7.0. Recommendations

Democratic Institutions must be strengthened through prompt action to reinforce checks and balances, make the judiciary independent, and protect electoral integrity. The institutions must be in a position to hold the leadership accountable and uphold constitutionalism.

Similarly, democratic governments must place emphasis on the tenets of good governance, prioritizing inclusive development, anti-corruption, and public service delivery to regain trust and legitimacy.

ECOWAS and the African Union (AU) must come up with the mechanisms and instruments that back up declaratory pronouncements. Sanctions must be timely, collective, and sustained until democratic order returns.

Civil society organizations and youth movements must be mobilized to demand accountability and substantive participation in governance processes.

Military professionalism should be saddled with the security of the state, lives and properties of citizens, while civilian occupy the seat of power, it must be institutionalized to prevent politicization and coup attempts.

References

- Adebanwi, W. (2022). Military coups and the fragility of West African democracies. *Journal of Democracy in Africa*, 3(1), 45–62.
- African Union. (2021). *Communiqué on the situation in Mali, Guinea and Burkina Faso*. AU Peace and Security Council.
- Albrecht, H., & Jackson, P. (2020). Security sector reform and the crisis of democratic governance in West Africa. *Armed Forces & Society*, 46(4), 643–663.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0095327X19873801>
- Aning, K., & Bah, A. (2022). The return of coups in West Africa: What went wrong with democracy? *African Affairs*, 121(484), 209–228. <https://doi.org/10.1093/afraf/adac012>
- Boas, M. (2022). West African coups and the myth of democratic progress. *African Affairs*, 121(484), 1–17.
- Boisbouvier, C. (2021, September 6). Guinea's coup and the death of West Africa's third-term democracy experiment. *Jeune Afrique*. <https://www.jeuneafrique.com>
- Branch, A., & Mampilly, Z. (2015). *Africa uprising: Popular protest and political change*. Zed Books.
- Bratton, M. (2013). Where is Africa going? The democratic recession and the search for political reform. *Journal of Democracy*, 24(4), 21–30.
- Bratton, M., & van de Walle, N. (1997). *Democratic experiments in Africa: Regime transitions in comparative perspective*. Cambridge University Press.
- Carothers, T. (2002). The end of the transition paradigm. *Journal of Democracy*, 13(1), 5–21.
- Cheeseman, N., & Klaas, B. (2018). *How to rig an election*. Yale University Press.
- Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches* (3rd ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Decalo, S. (1990). *Coups and army rule in Africa: Motivations and constraints*. Yale University Press.
- ECOWAS. (2022). *Report on unconstitutional changes of government in West Africa*. ECOWAS Commission.
- Gyimah-Boadi, E. (2001). A peaceful turnover in Ghana. *Journal of Democracy*, 12(2), 103–117.
- Hoffmann, L. (2023). Military coups and the politics of legitimacy in the Sahel. *Journal of Modern African Studies*, 61(1), 75–95.
- Mbembe, A. (2001). *On the postcolony*. University of California Press.
- Olonisakin, F., & Okech, A. (2020). Democratic governance, security and development in West Africa. *Conflict, Security & Development*, 20(4), 407–425.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14678802.2020.1787302>
- Prempeh, H. K. (2021). The return of the soldier: Africa's democratic regression. *Foreign Affairs*, 100(5), 15–22.

Van de Walle, N. (2001). *African economies and the politics of permanent crisis, 1979–1999*. Cambridge University Press.

Wing, S. D. (2021). Mali's double coups and the struggle for democratic legitimacy. *African Studies Review*, 64(3), 525–534. <https://doi.org/10.1017/asr.2021.75>